

The Role of Fractionalization in Estimating the Impact of Economic Shocks on Conflict

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Abstract

Assessing the effect of economic growth shocks on the likelihood of civil conflict presents significant obstacles due to endogeneity issues and omitted variable bias. I employ exogenous variation in rainfall across Sub-Saharan Africa from 1981 to 2009 as an instrument for economic performance. I examine whether the impact on conflict varies systematically with different levels of ethnic, linguistic, and religious fractionalization. Using an instrumental variables estimation, I find that while economic shocks alone are weakly predictive of conflict, their effects are significantly amplified in more fractionalized societies. In particular, countries with high religious diversity experience an approximately 7 percentage point increase in conflict likelihood when exposed to adverse rainfall shocks. Reduced-form estimates reveal that ethnic and linguistic diversity are also associated with substantial increases in conflict risk, potentially operating not only through income volatility but via other mechanisms. The findings demonstrate the importance of accounting for social heterogeneity when evaluating the impact of economic shocks on conflict incidence and raise concerns about exclusion restrictions in IV models of conflict.

Keywords: civil conflict, fractionalization, rainfall, Sub-Saharan Africa, instrumental variables.

1 Introduction

Civil conflict remains a persistent challenge in many developing countries, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa, where economic volatility and societal divisions often exacerbate political instability. Understanding the relationship between economic shocks and conflict is inherently complex due to endogeneity issues and omitted variable bias, which complicate causal inference. The underlying hypothesis of this research is that fractionalized societies may experience higher conflict likelihood during economic downturns due to weaker social cohesion, competing group interests, and limited capacity for coordinated responses to economic hardship. To address endogeneity concerns, I employ rainfall growth and levels as exogenous shocks to economic conditions in Sub-Saharan Africa from 1981 to 2009. Utilizing a first-stage estimation, I intend to demonstrate the relevance of rainfall fluctuations which serve as a widely recognized

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proxy for economic performance in predominantly agrarian economies, providing a credible instrument for isolating the causal effect of economic downturns on conflict. I argue that the exclusion restriction should theoretically hold as there is neither empirical evidence nor theoretical justification to suggest that rainfall influences conflict through any channel other than its impact on economic conditions. Prior research has extensively utilized rainfall changes as a source of exogenous variation to study the effects of economic shocks on conflict, development, and political instability (Miguel, Satyanath, and Sergenti 2004; Burke et al. 2009). Many studies emphasize rainfall growth rates, capturing year-on-year changes, as they better isolate transitory deviations from trend, minimizing concerns about unobserved, long-term differences across regions (Dell, Jones, and Olken 2012; Harari and La Ferrara 2018). However, relying solely on rainfall growth can obscure important dynamics. If a region experiences multiple consecutive years of below average rainfall with minimal changes between years, growth measures would misleadingly suggest stability despite severe environmental stress. Rainfall levels, by contrast, provide information on the absolute state of climatic conditions, allowing me to detect persistent droughts or cumulative resource scarcity that may exacerbate conflict risks over time. Using this dual approach, I investigate the existence of a differential effect when considering different levels of ethnic, religious and linguistic fractionalization; the methods used include a 2SLS and a reduced form estimation. The first stage includes both rainfall fluctuations and their interactions with ethnic, linguistic, and religious fractionalization indices, allowing the strength of the instrument to vary across different societal contexts. This setup enables the identification of heterogeneous effects of economic shocks on conflict across varying levels of societal diversity. To increase robustness and avoid potential violations of the exclusion restriction, I complement the IV approach with a simpler reduced-form specification. This model estimates the direct effect of rainfall shocks and their interactions with fractionalization on conflict outcomes, testing whether differential conflict responses to exogenous weather shocks exist independently of economic mediation. Sub-Saharan Africa is particularly well-suited for this identification strategy since agriculture remains a significant sector on which most people rely for welfare. While this approach is internally valid when using the population in the sample, it is less applicable to more developed regions, where weather fluctuations do not have a strong enough link to income growth, hence external validity is limited only to agrarian societies. Notwithstanding that the study is not global in scope, it holds significant value for both research and policy discussions, given the high incidence of civil wars in Africa over time. Sub-Saharan Africa is also one of the most ethnically, linguistically, and religiously diverse regions in the world. I account for the slow-changing nature of fractionalization by assuming it remains constant for each country throughout the model. This simplification is justified by the relatively stable characteristics of societal groups, which do not exhibit significant variation over the shorter time horizon considered in the analysis. Fractionalization is particularly critical since, unlike Europe or East Asia, where state formation led to linguistic consolidation, Africa remained dominated by small-scale societies, each maintaining distinct identities. Herbst (2000) argues that the absence of large centralized states over much of the continent resulted from

geographical constraints that limited the ability of rulers to project power over large territories. Similarly, Michalopoulos and Papaioannou (2013) demonstrate that African ethnic groups were historically organized in relatively small political units, contributing to the persistence of ethnic heterogeneity. The colonial era further institutionalized ethnic and linguistic divisions. The arbitrary borders drawn during the Scramble for Africa (1880s–1914) led to the artificial grouping of multiple ethnicities within single states, while also dividing homogeneous groups across different countries (Englebert et al., 2002). Religious diversity in Sub-Saharan Africa is another key dimension of its fractionalization. The region is characterized by the coexistence of indigenous African religions, Islam, and Christianity. Some regions of Africa developed strong, centralized states before colonial rule, which facilitated cultural and linguistic homogenization. For instance, the Tswana polities in present-day Botswana had a long history of centralized governance, with common political structures and cultural practices that reinforced a shared identity (Acemoglu et al., 2003). Similarly, King Moshoeshoe I, promoted a unifying Lesotho identity that persists today, contributing to its relatively low fractionalization (Easterly and Levine, 1997). In contrast, regions with weaker or more fragmented pre-colonial institutions, such as the DRC, did not experience the same degree of ethnic consolidation. These differences may be considered the root of conflict (be them differences of language, preference, religion, understanding). Using an empirical strategy I intend to test whether the marginal effect of economic shocks on conflict probability is conditioned by the depth of internal societal divisions while preserving causal identification. Section II reviews the literature on civil war determinants and societal fractionalization. Section III describes the data, while Section IV outlines the estimation strategy. Section V presents empirical results and addresses econometric identification, followed by conclusions in Section VI.

2 Related literature

The relationship between economic conditions and civil conflict has been extensively examined in the development economics literature, with particular emphasis on the role of exogenous income shocks in driving political instability. A key contribution to this field is Miguel, Satyanath, and Sergenti (2004), who provide empirical evidence that negative economic shocks, instrumented through rainfall variation, significantly increase the probability of civil conflict. Their work provides a compelling empirical strategy for isolating causal effects in environments prone to endogeneity. In my research I intend to expand on their intuition, building on their core identification strategy but by also exploring whether the effect of economic shocks on conflict varies systematically across countries with differing levels of fractionalization, an important dimension largely absent from their analysis. Ciccone (2011) raises methodological critiques about the robustness and generalizability of the rainfall instrument, arguing that the results in Miguel et al. (2004) may be driven by a spurious correlation between conflict and rainfall, particularly due to unusually high rainfall in t-2 being associated with higher conflict today. My results, however, do not replicate this finding; I find no significant evidence that rainfall levels two years in the past are correlated to

conflict risk today. Furthermore, Ciccone raises concerns about whether rainfall can be a valid instrument in less agriculturally dependent economies. While acknowledging this limitation, I mitigate it by focusing on interaction effects with societal diversity, which may themselves amplify the consequences of rainfall-induced stress regardless of agricultural dependency. A further re-examination by Miguel and Satyanath (2011) on their previous work does not manage to find any evidence of significant results when using more updated data; in contrast, the causal mechanisms supporting a rainfall growth specification are abundant in other studies. Subsequent work has debated whether rainfall levels or growth rates better capture economically relevant shocks. Rainfall levels (total millimeters of precipitation) are typically used in studies concerned with absolute drought exposure or agricultural productivity (e.g., Miguel et al., 2011; Hsiang, Meng, and Cane, 2011). In contrast, rainfall growth rates are more behaviorally grounded, capturing deviations from expectations or the status quo. This is motivated by insights from behavioral economics, including loss aversion (Rabin, 1998) and prospect theory (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979), which suggest individuals disproportionately react to negative changes rather than levels per se. Dube and Vargas (2013), for example, use negative commodity price shocks to demonstrate that unanticipated drops in economic conditions, analogous to rainfall growth, can incite violence. My paper adopts both levels and growth to explore which dimension better captures economic distress. Literature about fractionalization is also abundant; classical theories of ethnic conflict, such as Horowitz (1985), suggest that deeply divided societies face inherent challenges in achieving political cohesion. Empirically, Easterly and Levine (1997) provide robust evidence that ethnic fractionalization undermines economic performance by weakening the state's ability to provide public goods. More specifically, they show that fractionalized societies invest less in schooling and infrastructure, leading to lower growth. While this literature links diversity to developmental outcomes, my study explores whether fractionalization conditions the political effects of economic downturns. Fearon and Laitin (2003) argue that while fractionalization alone does not necessarily lead to conflict, it interacts with weak state capacity and economic distress to heighten the risk of violence. Distress which, in my analysis, is caused by rainfall changes that in interaction with a highly diverse society, increase the likelihood of conflict. More recent studies provide mixed evidence on the role of fractionalization in moderating the effect of economic shocks on conflict. Esteban, Mayoral, and Ray (2012) distinguish between polarization and fractionalization, suggesting that highly polarized societies are more prone to violence than merely diverse ones; while I do not directly test for polarization, I show that when considering economic shocks directly, also diversity, proxied by the different fractionalization indexes, is an important factor in determining conflict risk. Several empirical works also point to divergent mechanisms through which diversity influences conflict. Alesina et al. (2003) emphasize that ethnic and linguistic divisions reduce trust and coordination, while Montalvo and Reynal-Querol (2005) focus on how fractionalization affects the risk of civil war via institutional channels. My study suggests that economic shocks may exacerbate these coordination problems or governance failures in diverse societies, which helps explain the heterogeneous effects of rainfall shocks on conflict.

3 Data and measurement

3.1 Conflict data

Much of the existing literature on civil conflict has relied on the Correlates of War database. Nonetheless, many scholars have raised concerns about the COW dataset, with one widely noted issue being the use of an arbitrary threshold of 1,000 battle-related deaths to classify a conflict as a civil war; this standard risks overlooking conflicts that, while involving fewer casualties, may still be highly consequential, especially in smaller or less populous nations in Sub-Saharan Africa. An alternative dataset has been employed by Miguel, Satyanath (2011) who use the Armed Conflict Dataset developed collaboratively by the International Peace Research Institute, Oslo (PRIO) and Uppsala University. Compared to the COW dataset, the PRIO/Uppsala dataset offers a more transparent methodology and a broader coverage of conflict events. Notably, it records episodes of violence with a minimum of 25 battle-related deaths per year. I employ the same dataset for conflict in the African regions between 1981 and 2009. However, the PRIO/Uppsala dataset also has its limitations since it lacks subnational detail and does not disaggregated data by month, nor does it provide precise fatality figures. These constraints limit certain aspects of empirical investigation. Furthermore, the dataset's focus on state-involved conflicts does not capture other forms of organized violence. The primary conflict variable used in this study is a dichotomous indicator equal to 1 if country i experiences an internal conflict in year t that meets or exceeds the 25-death threshold. Using the 25-death criterion, 26 per cent of country-year observations indicate the presence of conflict.

3.2 Rainfall data

¹ I use monthly rainfall estimates from the Global Precipitation Climatology Project (GPCP), which provides a consistent record beginning in 1979, as a source of exogenous weather variation. The GPCP data are constructed using a combination of ground-based weather station gauge measurements and satellite-based observations of cold cloud cover density. Descriptive statistics (panel B of Appendix B.1) reveal substantial heterogeneity in rainfall across countries and over time within countries in the sample. This variability is crucial for accurately identifying causal effects when considering both rainfall levels and changes in rainfall growth. GPCP data is widely used and reliable for studying the spatial and temporal variability of rainfall, especially in climate-sensitive regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa.

3.3 Economic growth and controls

In my estimations I also employ data on economic growth (panel C of Appendix B.1) along with data necessary for calculating country fixed effects. This data comes from the dataset compiled by Miguel and Satyanath (2011), which is derived directly from Fearon and Laitin (2003) and World Bank databases. The fixed effects data includes democracy measures from

¹The dataset is available at <https://www.nccs.nasa.gov/services/data-collections/atmosphere-based-products/gpcp>.

the Polity IV dataset, the natural logarithm of per capita income based on World Bank figures, data related to temperatures inside the regions from Burke et al. PNAS (2009), and indicators for oil-exporting countries, defined as those where oil accounts for more than one-third of export revenues, also sourced from World Bank data. I have chosen not to include measures of income inequality, poverty, or unemployment rates as additional explanatory variables due to the significant number of missing or unreliable observations for Africa in existing macroeconomic data series.

3.4 Fractionalization measures

The measures of ethnic, linguistic, and religious fractionalization are drawn from the method used by Fearon and Alesina et al. (2003), both of whom construct indices that quantify the degree of societal diversity in a country. These indices are based on the probability that two randomly selected individuals from the population belong to different identity groups. This probability is computed using a version of the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index, inverted to reflect fragmentation rather than concentration. In this study, I use data for ethnic, linguistic, and religious fractionalization for Sub-Saharan African countries in the period of interest. These indices are treated as time-invariant in the analysis, under the assumption that group identities and relative group sizes change slowly over time and that the key political and social dynamics they reflect are relatively stable within the timeframe considered. The general formula used to construct the indices is:

$$\text{Fractionalization Index} = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^N s_i^2 \quad (1)$$

where: s_i is the population share of group i in the country, N is the total number of distinct groups (ethnic, linguistic, or religious). The index ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 indicates perfect homogeneity (i.e., everyone belongs to the same group), and values approaching 1 reflect increasing heterogeneity and diversity. (See Appendix A for fractionalization tabulations across countries.)

4 Estimation framework

This section outlines the empirical strategy used to estimate the causal effect of economic growth shocks in interaction with fractionalization on the likelihood of civil conflict. The main challenge in identifying this relationship lies in the potential endogeneity of economic growth: to overcome these concerns, I employ exogenous variation in rainfall as a source of plausibly exogenous income shocks in Sub-Saharan Africa. The identification strategy exploits the fact that in largely agrarian economies, short-run economic fluctuations are heavily influenced by weather variability, and in particular, by rainfall. I estimate the first-stage regression to show that rainfall growth is a valid instrument for GDP per capita growth by testing the relevance condition of the strategy using equations (2) and (3) (Appendix B.2).

$$\text{Growth}_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot \Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} + \gamma_i + d_1 \cdot \text{year}_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Growth}_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Rainfall}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{Rainfall}_{i,t-2} + \gamma_i + d_1 \cdot \text{year}_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

where equation (2) uses changes in rainfall growth at t and $t-1$, while equation (3) uses rainfall levels at t and lagged in the two prior periods. Both equations have a constant, country fixed effects which are contained in γ_i , and a dummy, $d_1 \cdot \text{year}_t$. I show the results of a first stage estimation of economic growth using rainfall variation, where both changes in rainfall growth and rainfall levels are highly correlated to annual GDP growth (Appendix B.2). The same is done for the estimation of the interaction term between economic growth and fractionalization ($\text{Interaction}_{i,t}$), estimated using equations (4) and (5) by the interaction between rainfall and fractionalization.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Interaction}_{i,t} = & \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot \Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 \cdot (\Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} \times \text{FI}_i) \\ & + \beta_4 \cdot (\Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} \times \text{FI}_i) + \gamma_i + d_t + \text{year}_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Interaction}_{i,t} = & \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Rainfall}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 \cdot (\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-2} \times \text{FI}_i) \\ & + \beta_4 \cdot (\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} \times \text{FI}_i) + \beta_5 \cdot (\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} \times \text{FI}_i) \\ & + \beta_6 \cdot (\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-2} \times \text{FI}_i) + \gamma_i + d_t + \text{year}_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The results of the first-stage estimations indicate a strong and statistically significant correlation between the instrumental variable and the endogenous regressor (Appendix B.3). For all first stage estimations, the relevance condition is also confirmed by an F-test. This high degree of relevance supports the validity of the instrument and justifies proceeding to the second stage of the analysis, where the estimated coefficients are used to assess the causal impact in the structural equation. I show the results of a first stage estimation of economic growth using rainfall variation, where both changes in rainfall growth and rainfall levels are highly correlated to annual GDP growth (Appendix B.2). The same is done for the estimation of the interaction term between economic growth and fractionalization ($\text{Interaction}_{i,t}$), estimated using equations (4) and (5) by the interaction between rainfall and fractionalization.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Interaction}_{i,t} = & \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot \Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 \cdot (\Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} \times \text{FI}_i) \\ & + \beta_4 \cdot (\Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} \times \text{FI}_i) + \gamma_i + d_t + \text{year}_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Interaction}_{i,t} = & \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Rainfall}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 \cdot (\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-2} \times \text{FI}_i) \\ & + \beta_4 \cdot (\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} \times \text{FI}_i) + \beta_5 \cdot (\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-1} \times \text{FI}_i) \\ & + \beta_6 \cdot (\text{Rainfall}_{i,t-2} \times \text{FI}_i) + \gamma_i + d_t + \text{year}_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

I present the results of the first-stage estimations, which indicate a strong and statistically significant correlation between the instrumental variable and the endogenous regressor (Ap-

pendix B.3). For all first stage estimations, the relevance condition is also confirmed by an F-test. This high degree of relevance supports the validity of the instrument and justifies proceeding to the second stage of the analysis, where the estimated coefficients are used to assess the causal impact in the structural equation. To isolate the causal impact of economic growth on civil conflict, I adopt a two-stage least squares (2SLS) estimation strategy, specified using equation (6).

$$\text{Conflict}_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \widehat{\text{Growth}}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot \widehat{\text{Interaction}}_{i,t} + \gamma_i + d_1 \cdot \text{year}_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (8)$$

For completeness, I also employ a reduced form approach using equations (7) and (8), to provide a comprehensive assessment of the relationship between economic shocks, fractionalization and civil conflict. The reduced-form approach offers a transparent and robust test of whether exogenous variation in rainfall directly affects conflict.

$$\text{Conflict}_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot (\Delta\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} \times \text{FI}_i) + \gamma_i + d_1 \cdot \text{year}_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Conflict}_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Rainfall}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot (\text{Rainfall}_{i,t} \times \text{FI}_i) + \gamma_i + d_1 \cdot \text{year}_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (10)$$

Equation (7) uses changes in rainfall growth, while equation (8) uses rainfall levels. This dual approach is used in all estimations as explained in the introduction. As in the 2SLS specification, these regressions include both country and year fixed effects, represented by γ_i , and $d_1 \cdot \text{year}_t$. This method does not require estimation of the intermediate effect on GDP growth and thus avoids concerns related to weak first-stage instruments or measurement error in economic data. It captures the total effect of rainfall on conflict, which may include both income-mediated channels and any potential direct effects. By comparing the reduced-form and IV estimates, I am also able to assess whether rainfall operates solely through income, or whether additional channels may be involved.

5 Main empirical results

This section presents the results corresponding to the identification strategy outlined in the previous section. I begin by reporting the second-stage estimates from the instrumental variable (IV) approach. The objective is to test whether economic shocks, instrumented using exogenous variation in rainfall, influence conflict outcomes, and whether this effect varies with levels of ethnic, linguistic, and religious fractionalization. While the first-stage regressions (Appendix B.2 and B.3), confirm a strong and statistically significant relationship between rainfall variation, economic growth, and their interactions with fractionalization indices, the second-stage results are less conclusive. Across all specifications, the coefficient on the instrumented GDP growth variable is generally not statistically significant, except in some cases when rainfall levels are used as the instrument. These findings suggest that while economic conditions influenced by weather shocks may correlate with conflict risk, the causal pathway from growth to conflict remains sensitive to specification and the strength of the

instrument, particularly when interacting with measures of societal diversity.

Table 1: Second stage estimation of Civil Conflict likelihood

	Rainfall Growth	Rainfall Levels
	(1)	(2)
<i>IV-2SLS, dependent variable is civil conflict incidence (t)</i>		
$\widehat{\text{Growth}}$	-.024	-.027*
	(.018)	(.016)
$\widehat{\text{Interaction}}(\text{Growth} \times \text{HEFI})$.024	.020
	(.022)	(.020)
R^2 (adj)	.6660	.6666
$\widehat{\text{Growth}}$	-.006	.070
	(.051)	(.012)
$\widehat{\text{Interaction}}(\text{Growth} \times \text{RFI})$	-.004	-.074*
	(.023)	(.046)
R^2 (adj)	.6688	.6700
$\widehat{\text{Growth}}$	-.023	-.026*
	(.016)	(.015)
$\widehat{\text{Interaction}}(\text{Growth} \times \text{LFI})$.019	.017
	(.019)	(.019)
R^2 (adj)	.6693	.6700
Observations	1073	1073

Notes: Regressions include country fixed effects, and linear country-specific time trends. Robust standard errors are in parentheses, clustered at the country level. *** Significant at the 1 percent level. ** Significant at the 5 percent level. * Significant at the 10 percent level.

The table 1 reveals that statistically significant effects emerge in relation to religious fractionalization. Specifically, countries with higher levels of religious diversity exhibit a 7% greater likelihood of conflict compared to more homogeneous countries when experiencing lower rainfall levels. Additionally, the results show small but significant coefficients for instrumented GDP growth, suggesting that part of the variation in conflict can be attributed to reduced economic growth caused by adverse weather conditions. Although the second-stage estimates do not consistently yield statistically significant results across all specifications, this does not invalidate the underlying identification strategy. Instead, it underscores the inherent complexity of conflict dynamics and highlights the potential need for more granular, disaggregated data. At the same time, the limited significance also raises concerns regarding the strength and validity of the instrument, particularly with respect to possible violations of the exclusion restriction. To further investigate the relationship, I compute reduced-form estimates that rely directly on exogenous rainfall variation.

Table 2: Reduced form estimation using Ethnic Fractionalization

	Rainfall Growth	Rainfall Levels
	(1)	(2)
<i>Panel A. Reduced form, dependent variable is Conflict incidence (t)</i>		
Rainfall (t)	-.100 (.066)	-.016 (.146)
Interaction (Rainfall (t) x HEFI)	.208 (.126)	-.109 (.256)
R^2 (adj)	.6662	.6662
Rainfall (t - 1)	-.113 (.109)	.153 (.148)
Interaction (Rainfall (t - 1) x HEFI)	.010 (.168)	-.433* (.247)
R^2 (adj)	.6681	.6683
Rainfall (t - 2)		.356 (.223)
Interaction (Rainfall (t - 2) x HEFI)		-.425 (.338)
R^2 (adj)		.6673

Notes: Regressions include country fixed effects, and linear country-specific time trends. Robust standard errors are in parentheses, clustered at the country level. *** Significant at the 1 percent level. ** Significant at the 5 percent level. * Significant at the 10 percent level.

Table 2 demonstrates that when considering rainfall levels from a prior period, more ethnically diverse countries experience an increase in conflict probability of over 40% compared to more homogeneous regions. These results align with the expectation that societal fractionalization plays a crucial role in determining the likelihood of conflict. However, no significant effect is observed when considering higher lags, such as t-2. A similar pattern emerges in Table 3 when examining linguistic heterogeneity. An initial counterintuitive 22 per cent increase in conflict likelihood in more homogeneous regions is offset by a 36% increase in conflict probability in highly linguistically fractionalized countries, relative to less diverse regions. It suggests that unexpected changes in rainfall growth initially destabilize existing social or economic arrangements, leading to immediate intra-community disputes and conflicts over land and resources. However, in the long term, more diverse groups tend to experience a higher likelihood of conflict. In contrast, different patterns emerge when considering religious fractionalization, as shown in Table 4.

Table 3: Reduced form estimation using Linguistic Fractionalization

	Rainfall Growth (1)	Rainfall Levels (2)
<i>Panel B. Reduced form, dependent variable is Conflict incidence (t)</i>		
Rainfall (t)	-.105* (.058)	-.083 (.113)
Interaction (Rainfall (t) x LFI)	.222** (.105)	-.008 (.206)
R^2 (adj)	.6696	.6693
Rainfall (t - 1)	-.085 (.087)	.103 (.100)
Interaction (Rainfall (t - 1) x LFI)	-.044 (.146)	-.360* (.193)
R^2 (adj)	.6715	.6710
Rainfall (t - 2)		.265 (.170)
Interaction (Rainfall (t - 2) x LFI)		-.264 (.287)
R^2 (adj)		.6704

Notes: Regressions include country fixed effects, and linear country-specific time trends. Robust standard errors are in parentheses, clustered at the country level. *** Significant at the 1 percent level. ** Significant at the 5 percent level. * Significant at the 10 percent level.

The reduced form estimates presented in Table 4 indicate no statistically significant interaction between rainfall shocks and religious fractionalization in explaining conflict incidence. This result suggests that, in the raw correlations captured by the reduced form, religious diversity does not appear to systematically moderate the immediate effects of rainfall variability on conflict outcomes. However, when using the instrumental variables (IV) strategy in the second stage, where rainfall shocks serve as instruments for economic growth, the interaction between religious fractionalization and growth becomes statistically significant (table 1). The significance of the religious fractionalization interaction in the IV results suggests that religiously diverse societies are more vulnerable to conflict when faced with negative economic shocks. As with all IV estimations, the estimated effect is attributable only to a subpopulation of compliers, which are countries that when rainfall levels are low, their conflict likelihood increases, while when rainfall levels are high, decrease in conflict probability. In contrast, the interactions involving ethnic and linguistic fractionalization tend to be significant in the reduced form but lose significance in the second stage. This pattern implies that ethnic and linguistic diversity may exacerbate conflict through more immediate, identity-based mechanisms, such as political marginalization, discrimination, or historical grievances, that are directly responsive to environmental conditions rather than purely mediated through

economic factors (Cederman, Wimmer, and Min 2010). Low rainfall levels cause crop failure which may lead to group migration, land conflict, not just to income loss. This would be a violation of the exclusion restriction, hence further research will have to be conducted. On the other hand, it can be argued for all estimations, that no exogeneity issues arise when considering whether conflict has any reverse effect on rainfall variation. This would be highly unrealistic, hence any exogeneity concern is solely due to the exclusion restriction.

5.1 Table 4: Reduced form estimation using Religious Fractionalization

	Rainfall Growth (1)	Rainfall Levels (2)
<i>Panel C. Reduced form, dependent variable is Conflict incidence (t)</i>		
Rainfall (t)	.063 (.074)	-.192 (.141)
Interaction (Rainfall (t) x RFI)	-.065 (.122)	.209 (.256)
R^2 (adj)	.6682	.6692
Rainfall (t - 1)	-.192 (.117)	-.245 (.152)
Interaction (Rainfall (t - 1) x RFI)	.147 (.188)	.267 (.266)
R^2 (adj)	.6713	.6701
Rainfall (t - 2)		.085 (.112)
Interaction (Rainfall (t - 2) x RFI)		.046 (.230)
R^2 (adj)		.6693

Notes: Regressions include country fixed effects, and linear country-specific time trends. Robust standard errors are in parentheses, clustered at the country level. *** Significant at the 1 percent level. ** Significant at the 5 percent level. * Significant at the 10 percent level.

The empirical similarity between the estimates using ethnic and linguistic fractionalization likely reflects the overlap between these two dimensions of diversity in some Sub-Saharan African countries. Moreover, the disaggregation of fractionalization into ethnic, linguistic, and religious components highlights the different ways in which social diversity can condition vulnerability to conflict. Religious fractionalization, often linked to deeply rooted norms, institutional trust, and inter-group cohesion (Alesina et al. 2003), becomes particularly salient when economic crises strain societal resilience. Conversely, ethnic and linguistic cleavages may trigger conflict through mechanisms that are activated even in the absence of major economic disruptions. Ethnic and linguistic barriers can directly affect coordination problems and service delivery, particularly in multilingual societies where access to education, justice,

or political participation depends on language fluency. This creates tangible group-based grievances which can affect many channels. Lastly, a key methodological insight is that rainfall levels, rather than rainfall growth rates, serve as a more reliable indicator of persistent environmental stress. While growth rates capture short-term fluctuations, they can overlook prolonged droughts or cumulative resource scarcity. The stronger results obtained using rainfall levels suggest that long-term climatic hardship, rather than temporary shocks, plays a more critical role in driving conflict in highly fractionalized societies.

6 Conclusions

This thesis contributes to a growing body of literature exploring the economic origins of civil conflict, particularly in contexts where state capacity is weak and societal cohesion is limited. Through the use of rainfall variation as an exogenous instrument for economic performance, the analysis establishes a credible identification strategy for isolating the effect of negative income shocks on conflict incidence across Sub-Saharan Africa. The main innovation lies in examining how this effect is moderated by ethnic, linguistic, and religious fractionalization, treated not as a composite index but as distinct dimensions of diversity, each with unique implications for group dynamics, coordination costs, and the salience of grievances. The analysis is conducted using both a 2SLS method and reduced form estimates. The empirical results show that adverse economic shocks, proxied through rainfall-induced fluctuations in GDP, are more likely to trigger civil conflict in countries with high religious heterogeneity. This effect for a subpopulation of complier countries, appears to operate through a mediated channel, whereby declining economic conditions in already fragmented societies strain social trust and increase the likelihood of violent civil conflict. Interestingly, while religious fractionalization exerts a statistically significant influence in instrumental variable estimations, ethnic and linguistic diversity are more robust predictors in reduced-form models. This divergence suggests that identity-based mechanisms, such as historical exclusion, language barriers, and inter-group competition, may influence conflict likelihood through more immediate, non-economic channels. These findings resonate with broader theoretical perspectives in political economy and conflict studies, which emphasize that economic deprivation alone is insufficient to explain conflict onset. Rather, it is the interaction between material shocks and underlying institutional or social vulnerabilities that generates instability. In contexts of deep diversity, shocks reduce the capacity for collective response and exacerbate distributional tensions, particularly where public goods provision is perceived as biased or inaccessible across group lines. This underscores the relevance of "horizontal inequalities" (Stewart, 2008), where inequalities between culturally defined groups, rather than individuals, are politically mobilized in times of stress. An important methodological insight from this research concerns the role of rainfall levels against rainfall growth as instruments. While much of the prior literature emphasizes rainfall growth rates as the preferred shock measure, this thesis shows that rainfall levels provide a richer signal

for persistent environmental stress. Growth rates may fail to capture the cumulative effects of sustained drought or prolonged resource scarcity, especially when year on year changes are small but absolute conditions deteriorate over time. The significant results obtained using rainfall levels suggest that longer-term climatic hardship, rather than short-term deviations, better explains conflict incidence in highly fractionalized societies. Rainfall levels thus offer a more stable and meaningful proxy for chronic economic stress in largely agrarian economies, strengthening causal identification where income measures alone might miss slow-moving, cumulative shocks. From a policy standpoint, the results imply that conflict prevention strategies in Sub-Saharan Africa cannot focus solely on economic stabilization. While safeguarding agricultural livelihoods and insulating economies from climatic volatility are critical, so too are efforts to strengthen inter-group institutions, promote inclusive governance, and reduce identity-based marginalization. Investments in multilingual education, equitable political representation, and interfaith dialogue could mitigate some of the destabilizing effects of diversity, especially during economic downturns. Moreover, international development frameworks should consider diversity not just as a demographic characteristic, but as a structural factor influencing political risk. Finally, while the analysis benefits from a strong internal identification strategy, external validity remains context-dependent. The reliance on rainfall as a proxy for economic performance is most applicable in predominantly agrarian societies. As African economies diversify and urbanize, the direct relationship between climate shocks and income may weaken, suggesting the need for updated instruments and micro-level data. Future research could explore subnational variation, incorporate disaggregated conflict types (e.g., riots, protests, ethnic violence), and examine whether social cohesion mechanisms, such as community institutions or local governance quality, condition the effect of shocks even within diverse societies. Despite some limitations inherent in the data and identification strategy, this study offers novel insights into how societal fractionalization conditions the relationship between economic shocks and conflict, highlighting previously underexplored heterogeneity in these dynamics.

7 Bibliography

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A Tables: Fractionalization by country (categorical lists)

A.1 Ethnic fractionalization brackets

0–25	25–55	55–80	80–100
Somalia	Tanzania	Gambia	Guinea-Bissau
Rwanda	Burundi	Senegal	Mali
Madagascar	Djibouti	Mauritania	Benin
	Zimbabwe	Niger	Liberia
	Lesotho	Ivory Coast	Guinea
	Botswana	Burkina Faso	Sierra Leone
	Swaziland	Ghana	Togo
		Gabon	Cameroon
		CAR	Nigeria
		DRC (Zaire)	Chad
		Congo	Uganda
		Angola	Kenya
		Zambia	Ethiopia
		Sudan	South Africa
		Malawi	Namibia
		Mozambique	

A.2 Religious fractionalization brackets

0–25	25–55	55–80	80–100
Gambia	Niger	Guinea-Bissau	Ivory Coast
Mali	Guinea	Benin	Ghana
Mauritania	Liberia	Burkina Faso	CAR
Senegal	Sierra Leone	Togo	Kenya
Somalia	Burundi	Cameroon	Zambia
Djibouti	Rwanda	Nigeria	Zimbabwe
	Botswana	Gabon	Malawi
	Swaziland	Chad	South Africa
	Madagascar	Congo	
	Sudan	DRC (Zaire)	
		Uganda	
		Tanzania	
		Ethiopia	
		Mozambique	
		Namibia	
		Lesotho	

A.3 Linguistic fractionalization brackets

0–25	25–55	55–80	80–100
Somalia	Mauritania	Senegal	Guinea-Bissau
Rwanda	Burundi	Niger	Gambia
Madagascar	Zimbabwe	Ivory Coast	Mali
Swaziland	Lesotho	Burkina Faso	Benin
	Botswana	Ghana	Liberia
		Gabon	Togo
		Sierra Leone	Cameroon
		Congo	Nigeria
		Angola	CAR
		Mozambique	Chad
		Sudan	DRC (Zaire)
		Guinea	Uganda
		Malawi	Kenya
		Djibouti	Tanzania
		Angola	Ethiopia
		Namibia	South Africa
			Zambia

B Regression Tables

B.1 Descriptive statistics of conflict, rainfall and economic growth

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Obs.
A. Civil Conflict Measures			
Civil conflict ≥ 25 deaths (PRIO/Uppsala)	.26	.44	1179
Civil conflict $\geq 1,000$ deaths (PRIO/Uppsala)	.12	.33	1179
B. Rainfall Measures			
Annual rainfall level (mm), GPCP measure	971	496	1073
Annual rainfall growth at time t	.020	.218	1073
Annual rainfall growth at time t-1	.021	.216	1073
C. Economic Growth Measures			
Annual economic growth at time t	.731	9.21	1179
Annual economic growth at time t-1	.643	9.25	1179

B.2 First Stage estimation of Economic Growth

	Rainfall Growth (1)	Rainfall Levels (2)
<i>Panel A: First-stage, dependent variable is per capita annual GDP growth (t)</i>		
Rainfall (t)	4.858*** (1.702)	5.787*** (2.036)
Rainfall (t - 1)	2.800* (1.419)	-1.880 (2.249)
Rainfall (t - 2)		-3.493* (1.806)

Notes: Regressions include country fixed effects, and linear country-specific time trends. Robust standard errors are in parentheses, clustered at the country level. *** Significant at the 1 percent level. ** Significant at the 5 percent level. * Significant at the 10 percent level.

B.3 First Stage estimation of the Interaction Term

	Rainfall Growth (1)	Rainfall Levels (2)
<i>Panel B: First-stage, dependent variable is interaction term (t)</i>		
(Rainfall (t) x HEFI)	8.829* (5.141)	9.793** (4.848)
(Rainfall (t - 1) x HEFI)	7.573** (3.541)	-3.481 (6.625)
(Rainfall (t - 2) x HEFI)		-10.746** (5.292)
(Rainfall (t) x RFI)	6.243** (2.519)	8.193*** (2.904)
(Rainfall (t - 1) x RFI)	3.011** (1.964)	-2.788 (3.582)
(Rainfall (t - 2) x RFI)		-3.318 (2.901)
(Rainfall (t) x LFI)	9.312** (4.080)	8.659** (3.342)
(Rainfall (t - 1) x LFI)	6.955** (3.219)	-4.285 (2.031)
(Rainfall (t - 2) x LFI)		-10.320** (4.748)

Notes: Regressions include country fixed effects, and linear country-specific time trends. Robust standard errors are in parentheses, clustered at the country level. *** Significant at the 1 percent level. ** Significant at the 5 percent level. * Significant at the 10 percent level.